

Small Particle Number Statistical Mechanics

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Traditional statistical mechanics is often formulated in terms of “counting” using factorials. The second step is to assume large particle numbers so that Stirling’s approximation can be applied i.e. $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$ and then maximization with respect to n together with the constraint e is applied to find the equilibrium distribution. In particular, factorial schemes may be used to calculate Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions (1). Recently, (2) have taken factorial expressions for entropy and applied them to low particle number counts, arguing one may have equilibrium even in such a case. In a series of previous notes, we have argued general equilibrium distributions may be obtained through time reversal interaction balance. This yields:

$\ln(g(f(e))) = -(e-u)/T$ where T is temperature, u chemical potential and g is determined from the physics of the problem

For the Fermi Dirac case $g = f/(1-f)$, but this applies to large particle numbers. Reaction balance, however, can also be applied to systems of small numbers of particles without this averaging (4). In this note, we try to examine the idea of time reversal balance for small particle numbers for the two physical cases argued in (2). We compare results from the time reversal balance approach to those from factorial entropy counting. It seems that for some cases, maximizing the small number factorial scheme leads to identical results as the reaction balance approach, while for other cases, it does not.

Factorial Entropy Counting for Small Numbers - Oscillator Case

(2) argues thermal equilibrium may apply to small numbers of particles, as few as 10. States are counted using factorials (without using Stirling’s approximation) and thermodynamic relationships are used to find T (temperature) and u (chemical potential). Two physical examples are presented. The first consists of n harmonic oscillators with a total energy of m^*e in the system, where e is the energy gap in an oscillator. The ground state energy is taken to be 0 and the $.5 \hbar \omega$ is dropped from an energy expression (as it is argued it adds nothing). (2) writes ($k=1$)::

$$S_{\text{microcanonical}} = \ln \left[\frac{(n+m-1)!}{(n-1)! m!} \right] \quad ((1))$$

where n is the number of oscillators, m^*e the total energy and the ground state energy is taken to be 0.

((1)) is very similar to a factorial expression used in (1) to calculate the large particle boson distribution. In that scenario, one imagines n boxes (with two fixed outer walls and $n-1$ inside walls) and permutes the $n-1$ inside walls with m quanta of energy. One then divides by $(n-1)!$ because the $n-1$ inner walls are indistinguishable and by $m!$ because the m quanta of energy are indistinguishable.

In fact, if one uses Stirling's approximation for ((1)), together with the constraint $m \cdot e$ and varies m , one obtains a Bose-Einstein distribution for m , which is interesting because there are phonons (bosons) which excite the oscillator levels. For the small n and m cases, however, analyzed in (2), one cannot use Stirling's approximation. T (temperature) is found by

$$1/T \, dS/dE \quad \text{or} \quad 1/T = S(n,m) - S(n,m-1) = \ln[(n+m-1)/m] \quad ((2a)) \quad (e \text{ is set } =1 \text{ in this result})$$

Usually, thermodynamic results apply to large n limits. Here, a thermodynamic large n, m limit equation is applied to a small particle number n, m case.

The calculation of $1/T$ in ((2a)), however, may be used as part of a maximization procedure:

$$S(n,m) - S(n,m-1) - 1/T [m - (m-1)]e = 0 \quad \text{which yields (if one insists that } S(n,m) > S(n,m-1)\text{):}$$

$$m = (n-1) / [1 - \exp(e/T)] \quad ((2b))$$

This is of the form of the Bose Einstein distribution with no chemical potential, just like the large n, m result. Here, however, e, n and T are constants, so this m maximizes entropy calculated using the factorial approach.

Small Number Reaction Balance and Oscillator Case

How would one treat the small number oscillator problem using reaction balance? The idea of reaction balance is to apply a probability balance to every reaction and its time reversed scenario. In this case, the total energy of the system must be E_{tot} , but there will be some free phonons and some excited oscillators. The energy of the excited oscillators is $m \cdot e$. Consider an oscillator excited to a level e_l which drops to a level e_j emitting a phonon. Then:

$$f(e_l) (m_{lj} + 1) = f(e_j) m_{lj} \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } m_{lj} \text{ is the number of phonons with energy } e_l - e_j.$$

This accounts for physical "boson" enhancement effects.

Taking \ln of ((3)) and equating to energy conservation yields:

$$\ln(f(e_l)) = \ln(f(e_j)) + \ln(m_{lj}/(m_{lj} + 1)) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{So } f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ and } m!k = 1/[1 - \exp(1/T (e_i - e_j))] \quad ((5))$$

((5)) may be applied to any reaction in an oscillator. There is an extra restriction that the maximum value allowed for e_i is m^*e . The normalization constant C is calculated using:

$$1/C = \sum_{i=0}^m \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((6))$$

This is a geometric series. Thus in the large m limit, $1/C = 1/[1 - \exp(-e^*/T)]$.

Thus, the probability in the large m limit for an oscillator to have an energy e^*i (i.e. a phonon absorbed into this oscillator) is $\exp(-e^*i/T) / [1 - \exp(-e^*/T)]$ which is not the Bose Einstein distribution for phonons ($u = \text{chemical potential} = 0$). The entropy in this case should be $-f \ln(f)$ because the distribution is of a Maxwell-Boltzmann form. Thus, it seems that the large m maximized factorial and large m reaction balance yield the same entropy.

Using the constraint on total energy gives:

$$N \sum_{i=0}^m C e^*i \exp(-e^*i/T) + \sum_{i=0}^m e^*i / [1 + \exp(e^*i/T)] = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((7a))$$

But one has to impose the restriction from (2):

$$n \sum_{i=0}^m C e^*i \exp(-e^*i/T) = m^*e \quad ((7b))$$

It is, however, not clear if such a restriction yields a solution for all n and m values.

A potential problem with this approach is that one assumes any "m" value represents an equilibrium situation for n oscillators. (It will be seen that arbitrary values of n and m do not always lead to a solution in the reaction balance approach.) For the factorial case with small m , we calculated above an m value which maximizes the entropy subject to an energy constraint, namely

$$m(\text{max}) = (n-1) / [1 - \exp(e^*/T)].$$

If one uses this m , ((7b)) becomes:

$$n \sum_{i=0}^{m(\text{max})} C e^*i \exp(-e^*i/T) = E_{\text{total in oscillators}} \quad ((7c))$$

With $m(\text{max})$ in the sum in ((7c)) and in the calculation of C , ((7c)) then becomes a complicated equation for finding T . From the factorial equation:

$m(\text{max}) e = E_{\text{total in oscillators}} = e(n-1) / [1 - \exp(e^*/T)]$ Thus, given a number for $E_{\text{total in oscillators}}$ and n , one may find a T value for the low number factorial approach. There is no reason this temperature matches that of ((7c)).

Furthermore, with the restriction of $m(\text{max})$, the normalized distribution function for f is:

$$f \text{ reaction balance}(e_i) = n \exp(-e^*i/T) / [\text{Sum } i=0 \text{ to } m(\text{max}) \exp(-e^*i/T)]$$

Using this in S density= -f ln(f) yields:

$$n e^*m(\text{max}) + \ln([\text{Sum } i=0 \text{ to } m(\text{max}) \exp(-e^*i/T)])$$

This does not seem to be the same result as using m(max) in $\ln [(n+m-1)! / ((n-1)! m!)]$

Alternatively, if one does not want to maximize m in the factorial approach, then one has two numbers n and m, (which seems to be the approach of (2) as no maximization appears). In general, it seems one may take n oscillators and add m*e energy of phonons, where e is the level spacing. There must, however, be a reaction balance, meaning only $m_1 < m$ phonons may be absorbed at any instant in time. Not all small integer values of m_1 may satisfy such a situation, it seems.

In ((7b)), n=the number of oscillators and e and m are known, so one may solve for T, the temperature. Given this temperature, ((7a)) shows there is a phonon bath with energy

$$\text{Sum } i=0 \text{ to } m e^*i / [1+ \exp(e^*i/T)] \text{ driving the } n \text{ oscillator system.}$$

For example, if one only had one oscillator, one would need a phonon in the bath at least part of the time. (This almost has the appearance of a hot nucleus with a vapour of nucleons outside. The m*e constraint describes the hot nucleus. In the literature there exist subtraction techniques for hot nuclei which use ((7a)) in such a way that the "nucleus" or ((7b)) has a certain energy.)

At first glance, the unmaximized small m factorial approach and reaction balance approach seem different. In addition, the maximized factorial case, also seems to differ.

Consider the simplest case: n=m=1. Then, the factorial approach yields $1/T = \ln(1)$ with e=1. This is a problem as T cannot be infinite.

Consider n=2 and m=3. The factorial approach yields $1/T = \ln(4/3)$ while the reaction approach gives $1/T = \ln(a)$ where $6=3a^3 + a*a -a$ with a solution close to 1.25. Thus, the two results are not the same.

Second Example: Factorial versus Balance Approach and Spin Up, Spin Down

Consider a system of n electrons with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ with m of them pointing up in a magnetic field. Let the down spin energy be 0 and the spin up energy be e . Then the total energy of the system is $m \cdot e$, but one must choose which electrons point up. Thus (2) gives:

$$S_{\text{microcanonical}} = \ln\left(\frac{n!}{m!(n-m)!}\right) \quad ((7)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{1}{T} = \ln\left[\frac{(n-m+1)}{m}\right] \quad ((8))$$

One may again find an m which maximizes entropy subject to $m \cdot e$ i.e.

$$\ln\left[\frac{(n-m+1)}{m}\right] = \frac{e}{T} \quad \text{or:} \quad m_{\text{max}} = \frac{(n-1)}{[1 + \exp(e/T)]}$$

which is of the Fermi Dirac form with no chemical potential.

For n and m large, ((7)) yields a Fermi-Dirac distribution for m if one uses Stirling's approximation together with the constraint $m \cdot e$ and varies m .

For the balance reaction approach, ((4)) still applies, but there are only two energy levels, the ground state and spin up. Thus: $C = \frac{1}{[1 + \exp(-e/T)]}$

The probability to have a spin up is $\frac{\exp(-e/T)}{[1 + \exp(-e/T)]}$. This is a Fermi-Dirac distribution with a chemical potential of 0. Thus, in this second example, the small n, m limit of both the factorial and reaction approach yield the same result if one uses m_{max} for the factorial case.

This appears in the factorial case, however, because one sets the spin down energy as 0. Otherwise, one would have $\frac{\exp(-e(\text{up})/T)}{[\exp(-e(\text{up})/T) + \exp(-e(\text{down})/T)]}$.

Thus: $E_{\text{total in spins}} = n \frac{\exp(-e(\text{up})/T)}{[\exp(-e(\text{up})/T) + \exp(-e(\text{down})/T)]}$ for the factorial result ((9a)) If one sets $e_{\text{down}} = 0$ as in (2) and $e_{\text{up}} = e$, then one obtains:

$$E_{\text{total in spins}} = n / [1 + \exp(e/T)] \quad ((9b)) \quad \text{versus} \quad (n-1) / [1 + \exp(e/T)] \quad \text{for the factorial case.}$$

Here n is the number of electrons and m is known, thus one may solve for T .

Alternatively, if one assumes any n and m in the factorial case, one assumes any "m" value represents an equilibrium situation for n oscillators.

For example, consider a single two level system as described in (3). One level has energy e_g and the other e_1 . Then:

$$\frac{\text{Particles in } e_1}{\text{Particles in } e_g} = \frac{\exp(-e_1/T)}{\exp(-e_g/T)} \quad ((10)) \quad \text{as given in (3)}$$

Thus, there is a very specific equilibrium result which agrees with the reaction balance approach. One cannot choose arbitrary n and m and have an equilibrium it seems.

Comparisons with using m max

For the factorial scheme with $n=3$ and $m=2$ one finds: $1/T = \ln(1)=0$ or $T = \text{infinite}$ so there is no solution. For $n=4$, $m=2$, the factorial approach yields $1/T = \ln(1.5)$, but the reaction approach yields $T = \text{infinite}$. This seems to suggest the constraint ((9a)) is more reliable than ((9b)). Not all choices of n and m represent equilibrium results although the factorial approach allows for any:

$(n-m+1)/m > 1$ choice for $1/T$ to be positive in the factorial approach

Again, it seems the factorial and balance reaction approaches are different if one uses arbitrary (not maximized) n and m , but are the same for this example if one uses m max in the factorial approach.

Reaction Model versus Factorial Counting

In general, factorial counting and even the reaction model are applied to large numbers of particles and seem to give similar results in such a case. The reaction model, in principle, however, does not need to apply to a large number of particles because it makes use of scattering probabilities and conservation of interaction energy. As an example, consider the elastic scattering: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((11a)). The probability to scatter equals in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the probability to find a particle e_i next to a particle e_j , thus:

$f(e_1) f(e_2) = f(e_3) f(e_4)$ Taking \ln of both sides and equating to ((11a)) leads to:

$f(e_i) = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ ((11b)) where u can be thought of as part of a normalization constant and T is temperature.

At this point, one has the distribution function and does not need entropy, factorial counting or a partition function. We have argued in (4), however, that one may map elastic scattering into the factorial scheme: $M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)$ ((12)). For large m_i , where m_i is the number of particles with energy e_i , using Stirling's approximation together with the constraint $\sum m_i e_i = E$ and maximizing ((12)) by varying m_i leads to m_i proportional to $\exp(-e_i/T)$. If one does not maximize ((12)), one has not yet found the equilibrium distribution, but a fluctuation.

Thus, the elastic scattering approach, which is not dependent on large particle numbers gives the same distribution as the factorial approach for large m_i . The idea of the mapping is that if e_1 and e_2 are next to each other in a factorial arrangement, they will interact. Thus, one needs to have e_1 and e_2 next to each other the same number of times as $e_i e_j$ where $e_i e_j = e_1 e_2$.

Consider next small numbers of m_i and a total energy of $\sum e_i m_i$ and maximize:

$$\ln[M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)] + \sum_i \frac{1}{T} m_i e_i$$

We use: $\ln(x!) = \sum_{k=1}^x \ln(k)$ from (2) thus:

$$S(m_{i+1}) - S(m_i) + \frac{1}{T} (e_i - u) = 0 \quad \text{or:} \quad \ln(m_{i+1}) = -\frac{1}{T} (e_i - u) \quad \text{or}$$

$$m_{i+1} = n C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad \text{where } C \text{ is the normalization constant of } \exp(-e/T)$$

Thus, both the factorial approach with small numbers, but using m_i which maximizes entropy is almost identical to the reaction balance approach. (The difference is m_{i+1} versus m_i .)

Factorial Approach with Stirling's Approximation and with Small Numbers

Given that the small number factorial approach with the maximization of entropy subject to an energy constraint yield identical results as the reaction method for two cases, it may be good to investigate.

Consider: $\ln[(n+m)! / m!]$ In Stirling's approximation this is:

$(n+m) \ln(n+m) - m \ln(m)$ and one may add the constraint $m \leq e$. Then maximizing with respect to m gives:

$$1 + \ln(n+m) - 1 - \ln(m) - \frac{1}{T} m e = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \ln[(n+m)/m] = e/T$$

For the low m and n approach, one uses from (2) $\ln(x!) = \sum_{k=1}^x \ln(k)$.

Then $\ln[(n+m+1)!] - \ln[(n+m)!] - \ln[(m+1)!] + \ln(m!) + \frac{1}{T} (m+1 - m) e = 0$ or

$\ln(n+m+1) - \ln(m+1) = e/T$, but this is almost identical to the Stirling's approximation result.

Thus, when maximizing in the factorial scheme using small n and m , one obtains pretty much the same result as using the large n, m result and Stirling's approximation. The question then seems to be whether the reaction balance approach in the small m case mimics the large m case or not. It seems for some cases it does, like Maxwell-Boltzmann elastic scattering, but for other cases involving energy in oscillators or energy levels in an atom, it does not. Thus, it seems that one has to be careful whether a reaction approach may map into a factorial scheme or not. For example, see (5) for a small particle calculation using reaction balance where one has to consider Pauli blocking. No Pauli blocking appears in the two examples chosen in (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the reaction balance approach seems to support the idea of small particle number equilibrium situations. In (2), small particle number equilibrium is examined from the point of view of microcanonical entropy which is defined as $k \ln$ of the factorial ways of arranging particles. Instead of using Stirling's approximation for large particle numbers, the factorials are kept, but $1/T$ is still obtained from dS/dE although a discrete change in dE is used. In particular, two models are discussed in (2), n oscillators containing $m \cdot e$ energy of phonons and n electrons of which m are spin up in a magnetic field. We argue that not all n, m values lead to equilibrium and compare the factorial approach with the balance reaction approach and find that the two are different, even when each yields a solution. In addition, T (temperature) is defined in different ways for the two approaches.

If on the other hand, one uses the small n, m factorial approach and finds the m which maximizes entropy subject to the constraint $m \cdot e$, the oscillator problem still leads to disagreement, but the spin example and two body elastic scattering are almost identical. Particle numbers differ by 1 in these two cases, so one needs particle numbers large enough that a discrepancy of 1 is not a problem. It seems that using Stirling's approximation for large n, m or finding $S(m+1) - S(m) + 1/T \cdot e = 0$ yield very similar results.

In this note, we argue that reaction balance should always be used, but it seems that factorial approaches, even for small n and m may sometimes map directly to the reaction balance approach.

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